

Financial autonomy of Italian metropolitan cities and provinces

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Financial autonomy refers to the ability of territorial entities, such as regions, provinces, metropolitan cities and municipalities, to independently manage their own economic resources. This independence concerns both the ability to procure resources through their own tools (for example local taxes, fees and tariffs) and the ability to decide how to allocate and use these resources to meet the needs and priorities of the administered territory. Financial autonomy is divided into two main components:

1. Revenue autonomy: the ability of entities to procure resources through their own taxes, share in the revenue of state and regional taxes, treasury or regional transfers and other sources of income, such as tariffs for public services.
2. Spending autonomy: the right of entities to decide how to use available resources, compatible with national and EU regulations, to provide public services, finance investments and ensure the socioeconomic development of the territory.

The level of financial autonomy of an entity is often measured by the ratio between its own revenues (i.e. those generated directly by the entity) and total revenues. A high degree of financial autonomy indicates greater economic self-sufficiency and less dependence on transfers from the State or other higher entities. Financial autonomy is essential for the proper functioning of local public administration, as it allows fiscal and spending policies to be adapted to the specific needs of the territory. However, it is balanced by regulatory constraints, such as compliance with the internal stability pact, and by the need to ensure uniformity and solidarity between the different areas of the country, especially to reduce economic gaps between North and South.

The analysis of data relating to the degree of financial autonomy of metropolitan cities and provinces by Italian regions in 2021 and 2022 highlights a general decline across the country. This trend reflects a reduction in the ability to finance themselves through their own resources compared to total revenues, a key indicator for assessing the economic self-sufficiency of local authorities. In the Northwest, regions such as Piedmont and Lombardy, traditionally characterized by strong autonomy, recorded significant drops, from 71.3% to 65.8% and from 80.7% to 69.9%, respectively. The Northeast also suffered a decline, with Veneto falling from 60.5% to 49.7% and Emilia-Romagna from 78.5% to 65.0%, demonstrating how the economic crisis or legislative changes may have affected these regions' ability to maintain high levels of autonomy. The Center, historically an intermediate area between the North and the South in terms of financial autonomy, also showed a contraction, with Lazio falling from 69.6% to 59.6% and Marche showing one of the most marked drops, from 81.1% to 62.9%. Tuscany followed a similar trend, falling from 76.2% to 65.7%. Umbria suffers a particularly significant reduction, from 68.7% to 48.8%. In the South the situation appears even more critical, with the South overall falling from 65.7% to 50.0%. Abruzzo records a dramatic collapse, from 81.0% to 52.1%, and regions such as Campania and Calabria also show significant drops. The major islands, Sicily and Sardinia, although starting from already lower levels, show substantial relative stability, although slightly decreasing. The overall figure for Italy, which goes from 67.4% to 56.8%, shows a uniform contraction on a national scale. This reduction can be attributed to multiple factors, including the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on public finances, the fiscal policies adopted and the drop in local tax revenues. The regional and macro-area analysis

highlights how the North, while maintaining higher average levels, has been hit by proportionally significant reductions, while the South and the Islands continue to suffer from structurally lower levels of financial autonomy.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. K-Means clustering applied to the 2021 and 2022 financial autonomy data identified 3 optimal clusters based on the Silhouette coefficient. The composition of the clusters is as follows:

- Cluster 0: Cluster 0, composed of Veneto, Umbria, Campania, Puglia, Basilicata, Calabria, Sicily and Sardinia, represents a group of regions with intermediate financial autonomy values, which tend towards the medium-low range in the comparison between 2021 and 2022. These regions, while showing non-critical levels of autonomy like Liguria (Cluster 1), show difficulties in maintaining stability or significant improvement in this parameter. The presence of regions from both the North (Veneto) and the South and the islands (Sicily, Sardinia) indicates that the decrease in financial performance is not limited to a specific geographical area, but reflects more transversal economic or administrative dynamics. This cluster highlights the need for targeted interventions, especially for Southern Italy regions, to improve the capacity for financial autonomy and reduce the gap with the best performing regions in Cluster 2.
- Cluster 1: Liguria, belonging to Cluster 1, clearly stands out as the region with the lowest values of financial autonomy in both 2021 and 2022. This unique position in the clustering indicates a specific structural situation compared to other Italian regions, probably linked to peculiar economic or administrative factors. Low financial autonomy could reflect a high dependence on state transfers or a reduced capacity to generate own revenues through taxation or other sources. This situation could be influenced by a limited economic base or demographic challenges, such as a significant ageing of the population, which limits the available resources. The clear separation of Liguria from the other clusters highlights the need for more in-depth analyses to identify the main causes and develop targeted policies to

improve the financial autonomy of the region, favoring its greater economic sustainability in the long term.

- Cluster 2: The regions of Piedmont, Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, Tuscany, Marche, Lazio, Abruzzo and Molise stand out for their high values of financial autonomy in both 2021 and 2022. This indicates a solid capacity for self-financing, probably attributable to more developed regional economies, diversified production systems and efficient resource management. These areas tend to benefit from greater independence in managing public revenues and expenditures, ensuring stability even in times of economic uncertainty. Their position in the high-end cluster highlights a stable financial performance over time, reflecting robust economic structures and higher income levels. However, the inclusion of regions such as Abruzzo and Molise, which historically show less dynamic economies than the others, could suggest a recent improvement in financial management or a positive effect of regional policies. These results highlight the gap between stronger areas and other Italian regions.

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